

Never Again War!

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Editorial

Never Again War!

Pope Francis' latest encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, published on October 4, 2020, covers a wide range of topics, most of which are secular in nature. The Vatican has released a synopsis, which begins with its own brief outlining the primary themes: "The Pontiff suggests that fraternity and social friendship are two approaches to construct a better, more just, and peaceful world, with the participation of all: individuals and institutions. With a resounding 'no' to war and globalized apathy." In this issue of our journal, we reflect also on what he has written regarding the inhuman wars we are capable of waging against each other, based mainly on *Fratelli Tutti*.

"Pope Francis says the coronavirus pandemic has proven that the 'magic theories' of market capitalism have failed and that the world needs a new type of politics that promotes dialogue and solidarity and rejects war at all costs." writes Nicole Winfield of the Associated Press (Isackson, 2020).

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Sylvia Poggioli, a National Public Radio contributor, agrees with Winfield that the two most important concerns Francis has addressed are an out-of-control neoliberal economy and the overwhelming role of war in contemporary political culture. “Francis argues the markets cannot fix every problem,” Poggioli adds, “and he denounces what he calls “this dogma of neoliberal faith” that “resort[s] to the mythical ideas of ‘spillover’ or ‘trickle.’”

Francis turns to the Catholic Church’s own doctrine on war, rejecting it as a means of legitimate defense, writes Poggioli on the subject of war and quotes the encyclical: “It is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a ‘just war’. Never again war!” (FT 258).

The concept of just war is dated. Despite its paradoxical character, just war has become an oxymoron that may have “made sense at a point in history when the concept of defense was truly about defense rather than acting as a euphemism for imperial-minded nation-states’ conquest and consolidation of power” (Isackson, 2020).

1. The Context

Military force and acts of violence, in Pope Francis’ opinion, are linked to an economy based on the “magic” of neoliberalism. Inequality is exacerbated by ideologies like trickle-down economics. They, he believes, are the root of ever-increasing inequity.

Francis is far from the only analyst to draw attention to the harmful link between the economics and the belief in legitimate conflict. President Dwight D. Eisenhower, himself a former general, memorably named the system the “military-industrial complex” in January 1961, putting the problem on the map. The fact that no US president has ventured to even mention the concept in public since Eisenhower, let alone criticize it says a lot about the magnitude of the situation today. Over the years, it has only become more monstrously fat. And the general public has become increasingly oblivious to this.

When it comes to a just war theory, we need to consider first, the Augustinian belief that war can be justified in exceptional situations.

The second is Francis' belief that no war can be just today, given the destructive power of violence (Isackson, 2020).

2. Historical Note

As Sylvia Poggioli points out, Pope Francis' views on just wars reflect a significant historical turning point. It's never been simple to justify war for a faith whose founder insisted on turning the other cheek. Christians glorified martyrdom in the early years, which often came as a result of turning the other cheek.

After Emperor Constantine's conversion in 312 CE, Christianity became the official religion of the Roman Empire, and the topic of legitimizing war arose as a moral issue. St. Augustine, writing about a century after Constantine's reign, created his just war theory, which became the Church's conventional position.

Rather than refuting Augustine's just war theory, which was elaborated by Thomas Aquinas in the 13th century, Francis uses Augustinian reasoning and the theory of proportionality to suggest a new interpretation of the theory. He claims that a rational justification for war carried out with modern weapons is simply unthinkable. The immense destructive capacity of contemporary weapons has pushed humanity above the point where a nation-state can justify war.

When US President George W. Bush used the pretense of seizing weapons of mass destruction (that didn't exist) to inflict immense and ongoing destruction in Iraq and the area in 2003, Francis may have sensed the terrible irony. What more ludicrous activity might be used to demonstrate Augustine's proportionality principle?

"We can no longer think of war as a solution," Francis asserts, "since its hazards will almost always be higher than its ostensible benefits." As a result, it is extremely difficult to employ the reasonable criteria developed in previous centuries to discuss the prospect of a 'just war'" (Isackson, 2020).

To put it another way, Francis has purposefully demolished decades of established political logic held by Christian Western states and the Catholic Church. It was frequently reduced to the basic notion that what we do is only because we are Christians. Augustine and Aquinas' somewhat delicate moral concept of a just war was often employed to cover up Christian nations' most severe kinds of military aggression, which were eventually followed — if not exacerbated — by the secular versions of most of those same states.

3. After the Ukraine War

The Vatican acknowledged that Pope Francis had spoken with Patriarch Kirill of Moscow, who had previously appeared to offer his support to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, in a statement released by the Holy See press office on March 16, 2022. "There was a time, even in our Churches, when people spoke of a holy war or a just war. Today we cannot speak in this manner. A Christian awareness of the importance of peace has developed."

"Wars are always unjust," the pope said, "since it is the people of God who pay. Our hearts cannot but weep before the children and women killed, along with all the victims of war. War is never the way. The Spirit that unites us asks us as shepherds to help the peoples who suffer from war" (Cited in Pillar, 2022)

The pope has been very active in calling for peace in Ukraine, even going so far as to personally visit the Russian embassy in the Holy See to ask for peace, while avoiding explicitly condemning the Russian government by name, as papal diplomacy has always favoured strict neutrality in order to press all parties for peace.

Ukrainian Catholic bishops, on the other hand, have frequently decried the Russian invasion as an illegal act of aggression, as well as the targeting of civilian population centres and the use of weaponry such as butterfly mines and vacuum bombs. Those same bishops have made repeated appeals for humanitarian and military assistance to the Ukrainian people as the country tries to fight the occupying force.

4. Francis and *Fratelli tutti*

In the current age, Pope Francis has spoken about the concept of a “just war” several times, including during the Ukraine conflict. His encyclical *Fratelli tutti* included a significant discussion on the subject.

“War is not a ghost from the past but a constant threat,” Francis wrote, calling it “the negation of all rights and a dramatic assault on the environment” (FT 257).

“War can easily be chosen by invoking all sorts of allegedly humanitarian, defensive or precautionary excuses, and even resorting to the manipulation of information. In recent decades, every single war has been ostensibly “justified”. The *Catechism of the Catholic Church* speaks of the possibility of legitimate *defence* by means of military force, which involves demonstrating that certain ‘rigorous conditions of moral legitimacy’ have been met” (FT. 258).

Further, he adds: “Yet it is easy to fall into an overly broad interpretation of this potential right. In this way, some would also wrongly justify even ‘preventive’ attacks or acts of war that can hardly avoid entailing evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated.” (FT 258).

The pope called special attention to the reality of nuclear, chemical, and biological weapons, which have totally transformed the deadly potential of conflict in recent decades. To quote him again: “The truth is that ‘never has humanity had such power over itself, yet nothing ensures that it will be used wisely.’ We can no longer think of war as a solution, because its risks will probably always be greater than its supposed benefits. In view of this, it is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a ‘just war.’ Never again war!” (FT 258).

This isn’t to mean that *Fratelli tutti* dismissed the concept of justified self-defense. “We are called to love everyone, without exception; at the same time, loving an oppressor does not mean

allowing him to keep oppressing us, or letting him think that what he does is acceptable” (FT 241).

“On the contrary,” the pope said, “true love for an oppressor means seeking ways to make him cease his oppression; it means stripping him of a power that he does not know how to use, and that diminishes his own humanity and that of others. Forgiveness does not entail allowing oppressors to keep trampling on their own dignity and that of others, or letting criminals continue their wrongdoing” (FT 241).

5. The Catechism on War

The Catholic Church’s *Catechism* opens by reiterating that “the fifth commandment prohibits the intentional loss of human life.” “Because of the horrors and injustices that all war entails,” it states, “the Church insistently asks everyone to pray and act so that the divine Goodness may liberate us from the ancient bondage of war.”

“All citizens and governments have a responsibility to act to prevent conflict. However, if all peace attempts have failed, governments cannot be denied the right to lawful self-defense as long as the threat of war exists and there is no international authority with the essential competence and power.” “The tight prerequisites for justifiable defense by armed force require thorough examination,” according to the *Catechism*, which also lays forth the criteria for evaluating moral legitimacy:

- The aggressor’s harm to the nation or community of countries must be long-lasting, severe, and certain;
- All other options for stopping it must have been proven to be useless or impractical.
- There must be realistic chances of success;
- The use of arms must not cause more harm and chaos than the problem that has to be solved. The destructive capacity of current weapons of mass destruction is a major factor in assessing this situation.

According to the *Catechism*, “these are the conventional criteria stated in what is known as the ‘just war’ doctrine,” and “the evaluation of these prerequisites for moral validity falls to the prudential judgment of those who have duty for the common good.”

The Catechism affirms the concept of a “just war,” but is clear that a “just war” is possible “as long as the danger of war persists and there is no international authority with the necessary competence and power” to stop it. Pope Francis effectively argues in *Fratelli tutti* that such international authorities now exist: “There is a need to ensure the uncontested rule of law and tireless recourse to negotiation, mediation and arbitration, as proposed by the Charter of the United Nations, which constitutes truly a fundamental juridical norm,” Francis wrote (FT 257).

“The seventy-five years since the establishment of the United Nations and the experience of the first twenty years of this millennium have shown that the full application of international norms proves truly effective, and that failure to comply with them is detrimental” (FT 257)

“The Charter of the United Nations, when observed and applied with transparency and sincerity, is an obligatory reference point of justice and a channel of peace. Here there can be no room for disguising false intentions or placing the partisan interests of one country or group above the global common good” (FT 257).

Pope Francis appears to be saying that the concept of two countries choosing war as a legitimate means of resolving their differences is outdated, and that when war does break out, it must be the result of a criminal act that necessitates a response, such as a police action by international authorities.

He is suggesting that the international community has developed sufficient institutions and norms that war is now a criminal crime, victims’ resistance is moral self-defense, and the international community’s essential intervention is a form of “police action.”

6. Pope Francis, John Paul II, and the Second Vatican Council

As Francis points out in *Fratelli tutti*, numerous wars have been undertaken in recent decades with the rationale that they were essential preventive or corrective interventions – Vladimir Putin has attempted to justify the invasion of Ukraine in this way.

Francis isn't the first pope to condemn unilateral military action outside of multilateral organizations. In the years leading up to the US-led invasion of Iraq in 2003, Pope St. John Paul II made several interventions, which were justified in part by Saddam Hussein's alleged possession and development of weapons of mass destruction. The pope was emphatic about states' moral obligation to use international institutions and laws rather than self-justified armed aggression.

St. John Paul II called for "respect for law" as a "certain condition" if humanity was not to "fall into the abyss" in his address to the Vatican diplomatic corps in January 2003. "Life within society – particularly international life – presupposes common and inviolable principles whose goal is to guarantee the security and the freedom of individual citizens and of nations," John Paul said. He added: "These rules of conduct are the foundation of national and international stability. Today political leaders have at hand highly relevant texts and institutions. It is enough simply to put them into practice. The world would be totally different if people began to apply in a straightforward manner the agreements already signed!"

"What are we to say of the threat of a war which could strike the people of Iraq, the land of the Prophets, a people already sorely tried by more than twelve years of embargo? War is never just another means that one can choose to employ for settling differences between nations." St. John Paul also cited the United Nations Charter and international law as prohibiting war "even when it is a matter of ensuring the common good," unless it is the absolute last resort and under very severe conditions (Pillar, 2022).

When compared to Pope Francis' own words on the matter, the two popes appear to hold quite similar views on the inacceptability of

states deciding when it is okay to go to war for their own reasons. Both are based on ideas from the Second Vatican Council.

The idea that a “international authority” would have a role to play in preventing war comes from *Gaudium et spes*, Vatican II’s pastoral council on the Church in the Modern World. It holds: “Divine Providence urgently demands of us that we free ourselves from the age-old slavery of war. If we refuse to make this effort, we do not know where we will be led by the evil road we have set upon. It is our clear duty, therefore, to strain every muscle in working for the time when all war can be completely outlawed by international consent” (GS 81).

Thus, Francis’ recent remarks on Russia’s invasion of Ukraine should not be interpreted as a type of pacifist manifesto, but rather as an explicit expression of what the Church has been teaching about contemporary warfare for decades.

7. The “Just War” of Augustine and Aquinas

As already indicated, the Church has traditionally promoted the concept of a “just war,” and has offered criteria for determining whether or not a war is just, both in terms of how it is declared and how it is fought. However, this theory was established and is based on a different understanding of war, when armies met in country fields for pitched battles, before the era of weapons of mass destruction, house-to-house urban combat, and the kind of “total war” that saw entire towns devastated during World War II (Pillar, 2022).

St. Augustine is credited with coining the term “just war” and giving criteria for determining whether or not a war is just. The *Catechism’s* own list substantially repeats these same conditions. Augustine, on the other hand, never regarded war as a good in and of itself; rather, he saw it as an unavoidable reality between states, kingdoms, and empires that should be avoided if possible. Francis acknowledges in a footnote of *Fratteli tutti* that Augustine “forged a concept of ‘just war’ that we no longer uphold in our own day.” He noted that he “also said that ‘it is a

higher glory still to slay war itself with a word, than to slay men with the sword, and to procure or maintain peace by peace, not by war” (FT FN 242).

St. Thomas Aquinas also talked about the concept of “just war” doctrine basing on Augustine’s works. Thomas further emphasized the need of a competent government declaring a “just war,” and highlighted that private persons were not permitted to wage war because the rule of law allowed them to pursue their grievances against injustice in a legitimate forum.

Francis’ perspective, which appears to be a development of St. John Paul’s own ideas, appears to be that, with the emergence of international organizations, states can no longer properly declare war as a means of resolving their complaints when there is a component legal forum to do so (Pillar, 2022).

8. Moving Towards Peace

Individual states now, the pope appears to be arguing, are like individuals who began military battles during Augustine’s time. From this vantage point, countries like Ukraine are victims of a violent crime, which they have every right to oppose and which the international community has every right to police.

As a society we should be moving beyond war, just as we went beyond slavery or colonialism. The collective consciousness and wisdom of humanity should make us realise the futility and injustice of war. Can we not collectively agree on that? For, we have been warned by John F. Kennedy: “Mankind must put an end to war, or war will put an end to mankind.”

In this pursuit religion, spirituality, politics and education can help us to lift our collective moral consciousness. Just like we have gone beyond slavery, colonialism and caste discrimination we need to move beyond “might is right” policy both at the individual and group level.

Let us hope and pray that we have the moral, political and spiritual will to promote our collective well-being.

The articles in this volume of *Jnanadeepa*, like that of the previous one, focusses on various aspects of Pope Francis' powerful encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, which provides us with a new and viable lifestyle, based on the Gospel values of fraternity, sharing and caring.

May all human beings learn to enjoy the Peace that comes from the Risen Lord, so that we learn to treat each other as brothers and sisters. So we can humbly listen to Martin Luther King Jr: "We must live together as brothers or perish together as fools."

The Editor

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